

KONVEKTIV KO‘CHISH HAMDA DEMFIRLASHGA EGA DIFFUZIYA JARAYONLAR UCHUN KOSHI MASALASINI SONLI TADQIQ ETISH

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Tabiatda uchraydigan ko‘pgina jarayonlar noxiziqli tenglama va tenglamalar sistemalariga orqali ifodalanadi. Shu sababli noxiziqli matematik modellarini tadqiq etish, samarali sonli yechish sxemalari va algoritmlarini qurish hamda kompyuter texnologiyalari imkoniyatlaridan keng foydalangan holda ularning dasturiy ta‘minotini yaratishga muhim hisoblanadi.

Maqolada parabolik tipdagi noxiziqli tenglamalar sistemasi orqali tavsiflanuvchi konvektiv ko‘chish va dempirlash hadiga ega bo‘lgan diffuziya jarayoni sonli yechilgan. Buning uchun avtomodel yondoshuv asosida qurib olingan boshlang‘ich yaqinlashish qo‘llanildi.

Kalitli so‘zlar: parabolik tenglama va sistemalar, avtomodel yechim, sonli usullar, Koshi masalasi, konvektiv ko‘chish, diffuziya.

Quyidagi parabolik tipdagi noxiziqli tenglamalar sistemasi uchun qo‘yilgan Koshi masalasini ko‘rib chiqamiz

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\left| \frac{\partial u^{k_1}}{\partial x} \right|^{p-2} \frac{\partial u^{m_1}}{\partial x} \right) \pm s(t) \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - b_1 u^{q_1} \left| \frac{\partial v^{m_1}}{\partial x} \right|^{p_1}, \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\left| \frac{\partial v^{k_2}}{\partial x} \right|^{p-2} \frac{\partial v^{m_2}}{\partial x} \right) \pm s(t) \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - b_1 v^{q_2} \left| \frac{\partial u^{m_2}}{\partial x} \right|^{p_2}. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$u(x, 0) = u_0(x) \geq 0, \quad v(x, 0) = v_0(x) \geq 0, \quad x \in R \quad (2)$$

bu yerda $m_i, k_i \geq 1$, $p_i > 1 + 1/m$, $q_i > 0$, $p_i > 0$ ($i=1,2$), $p > 0$ - sonli parametrlar, $u_0(x)$ va $v_0(x)$ musbat aniqlangan uzluksiz funksiyalar.

$b_1 u^{q_1} \left| \frac{\partial v^{m_1}}{\partial x} \right|^{p_1}$ - dempirlash hadi, $s(t)$ - konvektiv ko‘chish tezligi.

(1), (2) masala noxiziqli bo‘lgan ikki komponentali muhitda diffuziya jarayonini matematik modellashtirishda, g‘ovak muhitlardagi suyuqlik va gaz oqimi, politropik filtratsiya, sinergetika masalalarini va boshqa qator sohalaridagi masalalarni yechishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Masalan $u(x, t)$ va $v(x, t)$ lar diffuziya jarayonining dempirlash ta‘sirida konvektiv ko‘chishni inobatga olgan diffuziya miqdorini ifodaylaydi.

Ma‘lumki (1) tenglamalar sistemasi $u, v \equiv 0$ bo‘ladigan sohada buzilish xususiyatiga ega bo‘lib, klassik ma‘nodagi yechimga ega bo‘lmaydi. Bu holatda (1)-(2) masalaning umumlashgan yechimi o‘rganiladi.

Daslab $m_i = k_i$ xussusiy holini ko‘ramiz. Avtomodel yondashuv asosida (1) tenglamalar sistemasini avtomodel yechimini qurib olamiz. Buning uchun quyidagi almashtirishni amalaga oshiramiz.

$$\begin{cases} u(t, x) = w(t, \eta(x, t)), \\ v(t, x) = z(t, \eta(x, t)). \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{cases} u_t = w_t + w_\eta \cdot \eta_t, \\ v_t = z_t + z_\eta \cdot \eta_t. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$\eta(x, t) = x \pm \int_{t_0}^t s(t) dt = x \pm \int_{t_0}^t s(t) dt + c_1, \quad \eta_x = 1,$$

$$\begin{cases} w(t, \eta) = \left(|w_\eta^{m_1}|^{p-2} w_\eta^{m_1} \right)_\eta - b_1 w^{q_1} |z_\eta^m|^{p_1} \\ z(t, \eta) = \left(|z_\eta^{m_2}|^{p-2} z_\eta^{m_2} \right)_\eta - b_1 z^{q_1} |w_\eta^m|^{p_2} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Natijada (5) tenglamalar sistemasiga kelamiz. (5) tenglamalar sistemasida quyidagi almashtirish bajaramiz:

$$\begin{cases} w(t, \eta) = f(\xi) \\ z(t, \eta) = g(\xi) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$\xi = \eta \cdot t^{-\frac{1}{p}} = t^{-\frac{1}{p}} \cdot \left[x \pm c \int_{t_0}^t v_1(t) dt \right]$$

Almashtirish natijasida quyidagi taqribiy avtomodel tenglamalar sistemasiga kelamiz:

$$\begin{cases} -\frac{\xi}{pt} f_\xi = \frac{1}{t} \left(|f_\xi^{m_1}|^{p-2} f_\xi^{m_1} \right)_\xi - t^{-\frac{p_1}{p}} b_1 f^{q_1} |g_\xi^m|^{p_1} \\ -\frac{\xi}{pt} g_\xi = \frac{1}{t} \left(|g_\xi^{m_2}|^{p-2} g_\xi^{m_2} \right)_\xi - t^{-\frac{p_2}{p}} b_2 g^{q_2} |f_\xi^m|^{p_2} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$p_1 = p_2 = p$ bo‘lganda (3.1.7) quyidagi avtomodel tenglamalar sistemasi ko‘rinishida bo‘ladi.

$$\begin{cases} -\frac{\xi}{p} f_\xi = \left(|f_\xi^{m_1}|^{p-2} f_\xi^{m_1} \right)_\xi - b_1 f^{q_1} |g_\xi^m|^{p_1} \\ -\frac{\xi}{p} g_\xi = \left(|g_\xi^{m_2}|^{p-2} g_\xi^{m_2} \right)_\xi - b_2 g^{q_2} |f_\xi^m|^{p_2} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$f(0) = c > 0, \quad f(d) = 0, \quad d < \infty \quad (9)$$

(8)-(9) masala uchun avtomodel yechimini topish quyidagicha amalga oshiriladi:

$$\begin{cases} \bar{f} = f(\xi), \\ \bar{g} = g(\xi). \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$\xi = \eta \cdot t^{-\lambda}, \quad \lambda = \frac{1}{p}$$

Natijada (1) tenglamalar sistemasi quyidagi ko‘rinishdagi avtomodel tenglamalar sistemasiga keladi:

$$\begin{cases} \left(\left| f_{\xi}^{m_1} \right|^{p-2} f_{\xi}^{m_1} \right)_{\xi} + \frac{\xi}{p} f_{\xi} - d_1 f^{q_1} \left| g_{\xi}^{m_1} \right|^{p_1} = 0 \\ \left(\left| g_{\xi}^{m_2} \right|^{p-2} g_{\xi}^{m_2} \right)_{\xi} + \frac{\xi}{p} g_{\xi} - d_1 g^{q_2} \left| f_{\xi}^{m_1} \right|^{p_2} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

(12) ni asimptotikasini topish uchun quyidagi ko‘rinishdagi funktsiyani qaraylik:

$$\begin{cases} \bar{f}(\xi) = A_1 (a_1 - \xi^{\gamma_0})^{\gamma_1} \\ \bar{g}(\xi) = A_2 (a_2 - \xi^{\gamma_0})^{\gamma_2} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Bu yerda

$$\gamma_0 = \frac{p}{p-1}, \quad \gamma_1 = \frac{p-1}{m_1(p-1)-1}, \quad \gamma_2 = \frac{p-1}{m_2(p-1)-1}, \quad a_i = \text{const} \geq 0 \quad i = \overline{1,2}$$

$$A_1 = \left[\frac{(\gamma_0 \gamma_1)^{1-p} k_1^{2-p}}{p m_1} \right]^{\frac{\gamma_1}{p-1}}, \quad A_2 = \left[\frac{(\gamma_0 \gamma_2)^{1-p} m_2^{2-p}}{p m_2} \right]^{\frac{\gamma_2}{p-1}}$$

va $A_1, A_2 > 0$.

(12) da (13) almashtirish bajargandan keyin quyidagi sistemaga kelamiz:

$$\begin{cases} L_1(\bar{f}, \bar{g}) = -A_1^{m_1(p-1)-1} (\gamma_0 \gamma_1)^{p-2} m_1^{p-1} (a_1 - \xi^{\gamma_0})^{\gamma_1} - \\ - d_1 A_1^{q_1} A_2^{m p_1} \cdot (\gamma_0 \gamma_2 m)^{p_1} \xi^{\frac{p}{p-1}} (a_1 - \xi^{\gamma_0})^{\gamma_1 q_1} (a_2 - \xi^{\gamma_0})^{(\gamma_2 m-1) p_1} = 0, \\ L_2(\bar{f}, \bar{g}) = -A_1^{m_1(p-1)-1} (\gamma_0 \gamma_1)^{p-2} m_1^{p-1} (a_1 - \xi^{\gamma_0})^{\gamma_1} - \\ - d_1 A_1^{q_1} A_2^{m p_1} \cdot (\gamma_0 \gamma_2 m)^{p_1} \xi^{\frac{p}{p-1}} (a_1 - \xi^{\gamma_0})^{\gamma_1 q_1} (a_2 - \xi^{\gamma_0})^{(\gamma_2 m-1) p_1} = 0. \end{cases}$$

Agar $m_1, \gamma_1, \gamma_2 > 0$ bo‘lsa, u holda $L_i(\bar{f}, \bar{g}) \geq 0, i = 1, 2$ da quyidan baholanadi, agar $m_1, \gamma_1, \gamma_2 < 0$ bo‘lsa $L_i(\bar{f}, \bar{g}) \leq 0, i = 1, 2$ da yuqoridan baholanadi.

(1) va (2) masalani quyidagi to‘rda chekli ayirmalar sxemasiga o‘tamiz

Q sohada to‘r quramiz $\bar{\omega}_h$ X bo‘yicha h qadam bilan:

$$\omega_h = \{x_i = ih, \quad h > 0, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, n, \quad hn = b\},$$

va vaqt bo‘yicha quidagi to‘rni olamiz

$$\omega_\tau = \{t_j = j\tau, \quad \tau > 0, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, m, \quad \tau m = T\}.$$

va quyidagi boshlang‘ich va chegaraviy shartlar bilan sonli yechish sxemasini quramiz.

$$\begin{cases} u(t, 0) = \phi_1(t) > 0, \quad u(t, b) = \phi_2(t) = 0, \quad t \in [0, T]; \\ v(t, b) = \phi_3(t) = 0, \quad v(t, 0) = \phi_4(t) = 0, \quad t \in [0, T]; \\ u(x, 0) = u_0(x), \quad v(x, 0) = u_0(x), \quad x \in R_+; \end{cases}$$

(1) masalani oshkormas ayirmali sxema bilan almashtiramiz va ayirmali masalaga ega bo‘lamiz:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{y_i^{j+1} - y_i^j}{\tau} = \frac{1}{h^2} (a_{i+1}(y)(y_{i+1}^{j+1} - y_i^{j+1}) - a_i(y)(y_i^{j+1} - y_{i-1}^{j+1})) + c_1 v_1(t) \frac{y_i^{j+1} - y_{i-1}^{j+1}}{h} - \\ - G_1(y_i^j, g_i^j), \\ \frac{g_i^{j+1} - g_i^j}{\tau} = \frac{1}{h^2} (a_{i+1}(g)(g_{i+1}^{j+1} - g_i^{j+1}) - a_i(g)(g_i^{j+1} - g_{i-1}^{j+1})) + c_2 v_2(t) \frac{g_i^{j+1} - g_{i-1}^{j+1}}{h} - \\ - G_2(y_i^j, g_i^j), \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

$$G_1(y_i^j, g_i^j) = b_1 (y_i^j)^{q_1} \left| m_1 (g_i^j)^{m_1-1} \frac{g_i^j - g_{i-1}^j}{h} \right|^{p_1},$$

$$G_2(y_i^j, g_i^j) = b_2 (g_i^j)^{q_2} \left| m_2 (y_i^j)^{m_2-1} \frac{y_i^j - y_{i-1}^j}{h} \right|^{p_2}.$$

bu yerda $a_i(y)$ va $a_i(g)$, $i = 1, 2$ larni hisoblash uchun quyidagi formulalardan biri qo‘llaniladi

$$\begin{cases} a_1(y) = B_1 \left(\frac{y_i^j - y_{i-1}^j}{2} \right) \\ a_2(g) = B_2 \left(\frac{g_i^j - g_{i-1}^j}{2} \right) \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{cases} a_i(y) = \frac{B_1(y_i^j) + B_1(y_{i-1}^j)}{2} \\ a_i(g) = \frac{B_2(g_i^j) + B_2(g_{i-1}^j)}{2} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

(1) tenglamalar sistemasini yechish uchun oddiy iteratsiya usulidan foydalanamiz va quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{y_i^{s+1} - y_i^s}{\tau} = \frac{1}{h^2} \left(a_{i+1}(y) \left(y_{i+1}^{s+1} - y_i^{s+1} \right) - a_i(y) \left(y_i^{s+1} - y_{i-1}^{s+1} \right) \right) + \\ + s(t) \frac{y_i^{s+1} - y_{i-1}^{s+1}}{h} - G_1 \left(y_i^s, g_i^s \right) \\ \frac{g_i^{s+1} - g_i^s}{\tau} = \frac{1}{h^2} \left(a_{i+1}(g) \left(g_{i+1}^{s+1} - g_i^{s+1} \right) - a_i(g) \left(g_i^{s+1} - g_{i-1}^{s+1} \right) \right) + \\ + s(t) \frac{g_i^{s+1} - g_{i-1}^{s+1}}{h} - G_2 \left(y_i^s, g_i^s \right) \end{array} \right. \quad (17)$$

bunda $s = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} G_1 \left(u_i^s, v_i^s \right) = b_1 \left(u_i^s \right)^{q_1} \left| \frac{(v_{i+1}^{j+1})^m - (v_i^{j+1})^m}{h} \right|^{p_1} \\ G_2 \left(u_i^s, v_i^s \right) = b_1 \left(v_i^s \right)^{q_2} \left| \frac{(u_{i+1}^{j+1})^m - (u_i^{j+1})^m}{h} \right|^{p_2} \end{array} \right.$$

y_i^{s+1} va g_i^{s+1} ga nisbatan (17) ayirmali sxemalar chiziqli. y va g ning qiymati, y_i^{s+1} , g_i^{s+1} uchun boshlang'ich iteratsiya sifatida vaqt bo'yicha avvalgi qadamdan olinadi: $y_i^{j+1} = y_i^j$, $g_i^{j+1} = g_i^j$. Iteratsion sxema bo'yicha hisoblashda iteratsiya aniqligi beriladi va jarayon quyidagi shartlar qanoatlantirilguncha davom etadi

$$\max_{0 \leq i \leq n} \left| y_i^{s+1} - y_i^s \right| < \varepsilon, \quad \max_{0 \leq i \leq n} \left| g_i^{s+1} - g_i^s \right| < \varepsilon.$$

(17) ayirmali tenglamalar sistemasiga quyidagi belgilashlarni kiritamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{1i} &= \frac{\tau}{h^2} a_{i+1} \left(y \right)^{s+1} y_{i+1}^{s+1}, & A_{2i} &= \frac{\tau}{h^2} a_{i+1} \left(g \right)^{s+1} g_{i+1}^{s+1} \\ B_{1i} &= \left(\frac{\tau}{h^2} a_i \left(y \right) - \frac{\tau c}{h} v(t_j) \right) y_{i+1}^{s+1}, & B_{2i} &= \left(\frac{\tau}{h^2} a_i \left(g \right) - \frac{\tau c}{h} v(t_j) \right) g_{i+1}^{s+1} \\ C_{1i} &= A_{1i} + B_{1i} + 1 - \frac{c v_1 \left(t \right)}{h}, & C_{2i} &= A_{2i} + B_{2i} + 1 - \frac{c v_2 \left(t \right)}{h}, \\ F_{1i} &= y_i^s - \tau G_1 \left(y_i^s, g_i^s \right), & F_{2i} &= g_i^s - \tau G_2 \left(y_i^s, g_i^s \right) \end{aligned}$$

Natijada (17) sistema quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$\begin{cases} A_{1i}^{s+1} y_{i+1}^{j+1} - C_{1i}^{s+1} y_i^{j+1} + B_{1i}^{s+1} y_{i-1}^{j+1} = -F_{1i}, & i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1 \\ A_{2i}^{s+1} g_{i+1}^{j+1} - C_{2i}^{s+1} g_i^{j+1} + B_{2i}^{s+1} g_{i-1}^{j+1} = -F_{2i}, & i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1 \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

(18) algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi yechish uchun haydash (progonka) usulini qo'llaymiz. Ushbu metodga asosan

$$\begin{cases} \bar{y}_i = \alpha_{1i} (\beta_{1i} + \bar{y}_{i+1}), \\ \bar{g}_i = \alpha_{2i} (\beta_{2i} + \bar{g}_{i+1}), \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

bu yerda α_{1i} , α_{2i} , β_{1i} , β_{2i} - koeffitsientlar quyidagicha hisoblanadi:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_{1i+1} = \frac{B_{1i}}{C_{1i} - \alpha_{1i} A_{1i}}, \\ \alpha_{2i+1} = \frac{B_{2i}}{C_{2i} - \alpha_{2i} A_{2i}}, \\ \beta_{1i+1} = \frac{A_{1i} \beta_{1i} + F_{1i}}{C_{1i} - \alpha_{1i} A_{1i}}, \\ \beta_{2i+1} = \frac{A_{2i} \beta_{2i} + F_{2i}}{C_{2i} - \alpha_{2i} A_{2i}}, \end{cases}$$

bunda $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Boshlang'ich α_{10} , α_{20} , β_{10} , β_{20} qiymatlar yuqorida berilgan chegaraviy shartlardan topiladi.

Progonka usulini qo'llash uchun yetarli shart diagonal ustunlik shartidir.

$$A_i \neq 0, B_i \neq 0, |A_i| + |B_i| \leq C_i$$

Yuqoridagi ayirmali sxemalardan foydalanib, hisoblash tajribasi o'tkazildi. Raqamli tajribalar natijalari $h=0.01$ yetarlicha ayirmali sxema bosqichida olinadi va iteratsiyaning $\varepsilon = 10^{-3}$ aniqligi aniqlanadi.

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